

The Sound Development of First Languages Children Aged 3-5 Years

(Research on Naurah Dzakiyah)

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Abstract:- This research aims to describe language development of sounds in the first language of children aged 3-5 years. This research uses a qualitative descriptive approach. The data of this research were obtained from the speech of a child named Naurah Dzakiyah who uses Indonesian as her first language (native language). The data collection technique is done by observing, engaging, talking, recording, and recording techniques. Instrument used in the form of analysis sheets, recording aids in the form of mobile phones, and writing instruments. Data analysis used descriptive analysis with a longitudinal design. The data obtained is 424 vocabulary and 94 conversations. The results of this research show that the development of vocal sounds can be mastered by Naurah. Consonant sounds at the beginning of words often disappear when Naurah is 3-4 years old. The missing consonant sounds in the middle of words at the age of 3-4 years are /k/, /l/, /p/, /r/, /s/, /m/, /n/, and /h/. The lost consonant sounds at the end of words at the age of 3-4 years are /h/, /l/, /r/, /s/, and /n/. While at the age of 4-5 years, the consonant sounds at the beginning are not lost. Naurah's vocabulary is developing normally, judging by her ability to communicate and pronounce letter sounds better over time.

Keywords:- Development of phonology.

I. INTRODUCTION

Language is a tool for communication that humans use in interacting. All children, youth and adults can use the language. Language has a function as a tool to convey information by speak. speak the process of conveying information in that communication.

Linguists have lot of research, analysis, and talk about language acquisition. This research focuses on the study of first language development in children three to five years old. In psycholinguistic studies, language development in children is one of the processes of first language acquisition. In this regard, Chaer (2003: 221) said that discussing children language development has a point of view on the problem of language acquisition. In addition, Dardjowidjojo (Tarigan, et

al., 1998) reveals that children language development is marked by a dynamic balance or a series of units that move from simple sounds or utterances to more complex utterances. In other words, children language development can be interpreted as increasing children communication skills over time through the process of language acquisition. Therefore, this research was conducted based on the following thoughts.

First, acquisition is different with learning. Dardjowidjojo (2005: 225) said that acquisition is a process of mastering language that is carried out by children naturally when they learn their mother tongue (native language), while learning is a process of people who study in class and are taught by a teacher. Language acquisition or language acquisition is a process that takes place in a child brain when he acquires his native language (Chaer, 2003: 167). First language acquisition occurs when a child who was originally without language then acquires language.

Second, the phonological aspect becomes the first language feature mastered by a child in the form of sound. The ability to pronounce or pronounce words in child three to five years old varies. There are childrt hree to five years old who are able to pronounce words clearly, and some are not clear. In Naurah daily speech, which was observed from the age of three, some consonant sounds could not be pronounced properly, such as the phoneme /r/ which disappeared when she was three years old, then when she was four the phoneme /r/ became /l/. In addition, the phonemes /n/ and /t/ which are located at the ends, and the vocabulary produced by children inconsistent, especially in the initial syllables. This makes researchers interested in analyzing the development of child daily language sounds at home in family communication.

In this study, researchers analyzed the development of native language sounds in children three to five years old. The research subjects focused on the sound development of children 3-5 years old and research resources were also obtained directly from the researcher daughter in their daily activities. In addition, the researchers chose her daughter, because the way she spoke showing her language skills was different from her sibling. Lots of misspellings. In fact, every family member at home always communicate with proper pronunciation. The research interested to studying the

development of the first language in child from the phonological level.

II. METHOD

This research use descriptive qualitative approach. Qualitative research is defined as a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people or behavior that can be observed by describing the state of the object under study. This research was conducted in Ceurih, Ulee Kareng District, Banda Aceh. The data source for this research is the second biological child of a researcher named Naurah Dzakiyah. The data for this study are Naurah daily speech at home from three to five years old, from May 2020 to August 2021. The native language used in daily life is Indonesian language. Naurah interacts with the language at home not only with her parents, but also with her grandmother, father, uncle and her sister. The data collection technique used in this study is the method of observing, engaging, proficient, recording, and taking notes. The research design used in this study is longitudinal or cross-sectional. This longitudinal study is observational and naturally by recording the child's speech and behavior when speaking, both visually and auditory.

The steps in analyzing the data are as follows.

- Researchers record children's speech during conversations, both directly and recorded conversations. The utterances were collected to see the stage of language acquisition.
- Researchers identify data. Identification of data is done by examining children's speech.
- Researchers provide an explanation of the findings in the study.
- The researcher presents the results of the study and concludes the results of the discussion.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on research data, the phonological development of children includes the pronunciation of (1) vowel sounds, (2) consonant sounds, (3) diphthongs, and (4) clusters.

Based on the data that has been found, there are developments in the pronunciation of the research object, namely (a) the vowel sound is lost at the beginning of a word, (b) the vowel changes sound, and (c) the vowel sound is pronounced correctly. Furthermore, consonant sounds consist of; (a) a faint consonant sound at the beginning, in the middle, and at the end of a word, (b) a consonant changes sound at the beginning, in the middle, and at the end of a word, and (c) a consonant that is pronounced correctly. Apart from these, there are sound-changing diphthongs and sound-changing clusters. Overall data on sound development in children obtained is 424 vocabularies.

Based on the research results, there is a change in the vowel sound at the beginning of the syllable, such as the vowel sound /ə/ which changes to the vowel sound /a/ in the word 'jeruk' and the vowel sound /a/ changes to the vowel sound /ə/ in the word 'nanas'. In fact, the vowel sound that changes in both words is pronounced at the beginning of the word by dropping the consonant sound. Furthermore, the vowel sound /u/ changes to the vowel sound /ə/ in all parts of the vowel sound in the word 'susu' becomes 'səsə'. The change in vowel sound disappears and can be pronounced correctly when Naurah is 4-5 years old, except for the vowel sound /u/ in the word 'batuk' changes to a sound /o/.

And there are several variations of the sound changing consonants including; (1) Consonants change sounds at the beginning of words, (2) Consonants change sounds in the middle of words, and (3) Consonants change sounds at the end of words.

When a child is 3-4 years old, consonant changes its sound at the beginning of a word, i.e. the consonant sound /l/ changes to /d/ in the word 'lidi' to become 'didi' and the consonant /c/ changes to /s/ in the word 'satu' to be 'catu'. Meanwhile, consonants change their sound at the beginning of words when children are 4-5 years old, consonant sound /r/ changes to /l/ in the word 'rambut' to become 'lambuk' and the consonant sound /b/ to /m/ in the word 'bunga' becomes 'munga'. When a child is 3-4 years old, a consonant changes sound in the middle of a word, i.e. the consonant sound /g/ changes to /d/, the consonant sound /s/ changes to /c/, the consonant sound /p/ changes to /c/, and the consonant sound /r/ changes to /l/. Meanwhile, consonants change sound in the middle of a word when children aged 4-5 years only find a consonant sound /r/ which changes to /l/.

When a child is 3-4 years old, consonant changes its sound at the end of a word, i.e. the consonant sound /t/ changes to /k/, the consonant sound /n/ changes to /ŋ/, and the consonant sound /r/ changes to /l/. And consonants that change sound at the end of words are still found in the same words when children are 4-5 years old. Some words are well mentioned from earlier ages when spoken by a child. Changes in other consonant sounds at the age of 4-5 years, namely the consonant sound /k/ changes to /p/ in the word 'lipstik' it is pronounced 'listip'.

Based on the data obtained, the diphthongs found are /ai/ and /au/ diphthongs. Diphthong sounds don't appear much when children are 3-4 years old. The diphthong /ai/ becomes /e/ in the word 'pakai' becomes 'pakek'. Likewise, when children are 4-5 years old, the diphthong /ai/ changes to /e/ in the words 'cabe' and 'rame'.

The cluster sounds found are /str/, /pl/, /ny/, /ng/, /tr/, and /kr/. Cluster sounds at the beginning of words experience dissipation when children are 3-4 years old. Meanwhile, the sound of the cluster is also not pronounced perfectly when

children aged 4-5 years the word 'krayon' becomes 'kayon', except for the cluster sound /ⁿ/.

The /ny/ cluster sound in the middle of a word can be pronounced correctly at the age of 3-5 years. Meanwhile, some /ⁿ/ sounds in the middle of words disappear when they are 3-4 years old. The sound of disappearance occurs when the cluster /ⁿ/ meets the consonant /g/. Also, the cluster /tr/ cannot be pronounced correctly when a child is 3-4 years old, but can be pronounced correctly when a child is 4-5 years old. The cluster sound /ⁿ/ at the end of words disappears when they are 3-5 years old, except for the word 'tolong' which can be pronounced correctly. Meanwhile, the sound /ⁿ/ at the end of words can be pronounced correctly at the age of 4-5 years.

IV. CONCLUSION

From this study it can be concluded that the development of first language sounds in Naurah develops over time. All vowel sounds have been mastered, whether they are located at the beginning of a word, in the middle or at the end of a word. The consonant sound at the beginning of a word often disappears when Naurah is 3-4 years old. Even at this age, the first syllables are also lost. Lost consonants in the middle of words at this age are /k/, /l/, /p/, /r/, /s/, /m/, /n/, and /h/. Lost consonants at the end of words at the age of 3-4 years are /h/, /l/, /r/, /s/, and /n/. Whereas at the age of 4-5 years, no consonant sounds at the beginning are lost. Lost consonants in the middle are /k/, /l/, /r/, and /n/, and vowel consonants at the end are /n/ and /s/. Consonants change sound because they have the same place of articulation, namely /s/ becomes /c/, /b/ becomes /m/, and /r/ becomes /l/. Consonants change sound because they have the same way of articulation, namely /g/ becomes /d/, /t/ becomes /k/, and /n/ becomes /ⁿ/. In addition, Naurah has mastered the diphthongs /ai/ and /au/, as well as cluster sounds, namely /ⁿ/, /tr/, and /ⁿ/. The consonant sounds that do not appear until the age of five are the velar fricative [x] and the labiodental fricative [v].

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